

EMPOWERING INFORMED DECISIONS: POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR INTERMEDIATE STUDENTS' AWARENESS ON DISCIPLINE SELECTION FOR FUTURE STUDIES

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Abstract

This policy brief addresses the critical issue of uninformed subject selection by intermediate students transitioning to undergraduate programs. Many students make poorly aligned choices due to lack of awareness, external pressures, or insufficient career guidance, leading to long-term academic and professional consequences. The brief highlights the importance of aligning subject selection for helping students to make more thoughtful and informed choices. It recommends that educational institutions offering intermediate programs should take practical steps like organizing awareness sessions, offering career counseling, and helping students to explore their interests, so they can confidently choose a path that suits them and supports their future success.

INTRODUCTION

Problem statement:

The selection of undergrad subjects is a very crucial for students' academic career, as it acts like a bridge between higher secondary education and the profession that student wants to adopt in future. This policy brief focuses on the importance of consideration when choosing undergraduate subjects at university level. So, the choice of undergraduate subjects should align to the student's future ambitions and personal interests. Educational path in a university for a student is like a chemical solution with ingredients of undergraduate subjects as solvent and interest of student as solute, which can change the taste of life by getting a good job for a bright future.

After the completion of higher secondary education, choosing a suitable discipline is a major task for

students. At this stage, students face many problems, such as mostly having no idea about the discipline of their interest or about the strengths or weaknesses in their selected subjects for the undergraduate program. Sometimes, students are forced by their friends and family members to choose a specific subject that does not match with student's own interest, is called choice-by-force. So if they choose such kind of imposed subjects, they always face difficulties to align with their interests. This weakly aligned choice, on the one side, always remain problematic for the students to easily understand the basic or advanced concepts; while on other side, narrow down the choice of profession in post education. Our random survey of walk-in candidates for Fall 2024 admissions in five public and private universities in Sargodha revealed an interesting fact:

out of a total of 75 candidates (15 from each university campus), 40 had no clear choice of admission. These candidates were not even aware of the names of the offered disciplines and had been referred by their friends or relatives to specific programs. As a result, they lacked the maturity to understand the significance of highly important programs and instead leaned toward a few trending ones. When asked in our survey whether they received any guidance at the school or higher secondary education level, 57 candidates reported no such awareness. This lack of students' awareness from the host institutions regarding the merits and benefits of various disciplines, compromised the students' ability to make informed decisions when choosing the best discipline for higher studies and future professional career. Secondly, students also hesitate to openly talk with their parents about choosing undergraduate subject according to their interests as well as according to industry demand.

Objective:

The main objective of this brief is to create awareness for the higher and secondary educational institutions to extend awareness sessions for the senior students before approaching to the higher degree programs enabling them to choose the best discipline aligned with their interest, meeting the market needs and useful for their professional career.

Policy Recommendations:

This policy brief is proposed to get the attention of all educational institutions that offered intermediate programs to create awareness for their senior students about the:

- understand the current market needs
- choice of better university providing quality education
- recognize students' own interests and how they can align it with offering disciplines
- preference of discipline and its significance for the better professional career.

For achieve policy recommendations, intermediate offering institutions should conduct seminars and awareness sessions for the senior students where industry experts can share the current market need, while university experts can share the information of offering disciplines and programs aligned with

national and international market needs. This way, students will be able to choose the better institution and program rather the imposed decision. In addition, institutions should conduct study tours of intermediate students in different departments of universities to make their personal interaction with professors and under study graduates. Professors can guide about and the scope of offering disciplines; while under study students can share their learning experiences with the candidates. In addition, students' visit to the industry can make them well informed about the current market need would enable them to choose the better decision for the higher studies.

Understanding the market need and offering programs would enable the students to convince themselves and the parents for the better decision making in choosing the institution and right program. Pursuing a subject of own interest will genuinely make the students more passionate, innovative, and creative thinker to choose the better future.

